

RESPONSE PAPER

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-13)
3. Some rules of thumb for writing paper (EUCLID 2019, 14-16)
4. Literature Review (EUCLID 2019, 17-23)
5. What is a style guide? (EUCLID 2019, 24-26)
6. American and British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
7. Chicago rules Turabian (EUCLID 2019, 44-55)

WORKING IN AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

Being francophone, I learnt more than expected. Going through this first coursepack, developed by Prof. Cleenewerck, Laurent and Dr. Kabiru Gulma, I found a helpful and easy academic works to assimilate.

On the one hand, I have a better understanding on how we should proceed in an academic work, writing an essay. “Although there are some basic steps to writing an assignment, essay writing is not a linear process. You might work through the different stages a number of times in the course of writing an essay” (EUCLID 2019, 1). Preparing a Response Paper (RP), a structure is always to define in our work’s presentation. The focus recommended should be in reading and researching, giving us more tips in writing clearly and in a concise manner.

On the other hand, templates shared give us a logical flow of structuring ideas with word styles (headings), understanding punctuation’s rules in UK and US spelling. The more essential will be, how we will present it as well as which words are to be used? Our own words show honest and intellectual abilities, efforts from a writer. After reading, we understand well the writer’s ideas to develop.

How to write an essay? What is plagiarism? How to avoid it? Some tips on how and which style to use will be an added value for academic tasks. At which level can we consider this academic task? how materials are helpful?

2) ESSAY WRITING

Our opening chapter with works assigned in the ACA-401 coursepack for period one (1) give us a structure on organizing an academic work. I never realized in the past these differences are existing. Evidence is the common word going through these materials. The work is only based on showing proof of what we are doing and giving to our readers a better understanding of our inputs. From the beginning to the end of an essay, the plan will define how and what we will consider in this work assigned. In short words “our starting point for an essay is your initial response to the topic or question. This response is based on what you already know. However, this is only the starting point. You then need to research, question your response and find some answers” (ibid.). The core and most important is how ideas from our answers have to be developed in our essay to have different stages well organized. The writer should know how these ideas can be formatted to become an answer to question addressed during an essay.

Taking notes are recommended while reading. Its gives you an organization in ideas. An imperative is, the essay should be referenced avoiding any plagiarism in all respected academic works: “All academic essays MUST contain references. Referencing guards against plagiarism, a serious academic offence” (EUCLID 2019, 4).

a) PLAGIARISM

Most students failed in plagiarism due to lack of investigations and restituting academic works from researchers without citing sources. Referencing will be our guide where plagiarism is not allowed. The coursepack in ACA-401, videos presented by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck, pdf files are at all levels, knowledge for better understanding on how writing in academic environments.

Giving a definition: “plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of the source information” (EUCLID 2019, 5).

The quote style is in use instead of quotations marks in long sentences. When quoting a lot in academic works, paraphrases are the alternative for better presentation: “In a paper, it does not look very good if you have too many quotes. So, you will need to paraphrase at times” (EUCLID 2019, 8). When abusing in citations we will arrive at that point, the work will be totally not an academic work with some consequences, affecting the writer. The recommended answer will be citations to avoid any undesirable and unformal restitution of the work assigned. When we have in text citation what we would do simply: “when you cite something in the text of your paper, you simply need only to put the author 's name in parenthesis with the page number that the information came from” (EUCLID 2019, 5).

In all academic works, to avoid plagiarism, citations must be adopted. Using short quotations and long quotations (no quotations marks if it is more than 5 lines).

An alternative, where having a lot of quotes in an essay, is working properly to use paraphrases some times and not abusing. In your own words, author production, will be given back to a lecturer without distortions. The quote style used and rules adopted will accompany the academic work. Readers should know all the time in which part we took our ideas if not yours. Its helps to understand our intention, our scope to give a credit in our restitution and what we are explaining. I am totally agreed that this is our first definition before being intellectuals, we need to be more honest and follow a certain flow which is really clear for all readers.

b) Some rules of thumb for writing paper

As part of the work assigned rules are strictly important which conduct the core of the work to present in front of an academic essay. The main purpose is to have concise, clear as well as understandable work. Seriousness in what we retribute in an academic writing shows evidence of intellectual effort from the writer. When writing clearly, a special touch is brought. Some important rules are to be followed in order to have a work referenced.

The first recommendation in writing will be to be focused:

For example, if you are writing in criticism of John Rawls's "difference principle," you should not try to sketch his theory of the original position and the argument for the principle within the original position. Confine yourself to the aspects of Rawls's view that are of immediate relevance to his account of fair distribution. Anything else will be a distraction, and, in the short space available, is not likely to be done well (EUCLID 2019, 14).

Most important other rules are to be followed to give a credit to your words: "write clearly," "do not make the writing boring and clumsy," "support assertions," "take the views you are discussing seriously," "do not plagiarize" (EUCLID 2019, 14-16). At the end, taking in consideration these rules, all academic records will be at the level expected with your own words and logical flow in ideas and presentation. Such work will be appreciated if a literature review is done by the writer.

I found these rules very explanative and practical for students in research of right inputs for their academic presentations. I can focus on these special recommendations to retribute a presentation in rules of art.

c) Literature review

Writing is calling a set of rules to be respected to avoid any kind of mistakes. In English UK as well as in US English, things can change, bring variance in the perception even the meaning of words as defined: "American and British English are both variants of World English. As such, they are more similar than different, especially with "educated"

or “scientific” English. Most divergence can be ascribed to differing national histories and cultural development” (<https://www.pbs.org/speak/ahead/>).

Grammar, syntax and punctuation, the core of academic works bring a touch where used and how used. They will give different meanings to words, phrases, expressing our feelings, our ideas learned as well as our knowledge about the subject. How to pronounce or spell will participate to clarify in which context we are speaking and the subject we are dealing with: the context will be defined.

The punctuation used in works is very important. This is to clarify, in how and when we have to put a period in our sentences. Differences arise anytime in considering the place for a period, placed outside or inside a quotation mark. As mentioned, we are not the only one with doubts, having ideas to put a period within the quotation mark:

I’ve always thought that the standard practice, in this case, can lead to confusion in many, many sentences, especially in direct quotes taken from the middle of a sentence. Putting a period within the quotation marks just because a "rule" tells us to can in certain situations imply that the original author of the sentence had a period in that spot too. I think that EVERYTHING (except ellipses) within a direct quotation should be identical to the original author's text. That said, ALL grammarians that I have encountered have supported the rule that ALL PUNCTUATION GOES INSIDE QUOTATION MARKS IN AMERICAN PRACTICE (EUCLID 2019, 19).

Our modern world brings also use of creativity in the way expressing ourselves. Words are created and contextualized to bring a touch of invention and making “fashionable” the perception we could have on them. We will be in a modern world “Googling” and “Twittering” referring to the words google and Twitter (EUCLID 2019, 31).

It arises we have in many contexts, even equality in vocabulary. Words can be replaced by other which have the same meaning. Some examples can be given: “policeman/ police officer,” “salesman/ salesperson” (EUCLID 2019, 32). I guess, understanding our interlocutor was not difficult. Any of these expressions, will be understood because it depends on the choice of whom expresses them properly.

In my opinion, ambiguity in our works are related to using punctuation where not needed. Grammatically examples are numerous, where to put a comma, periods, quotation marks. These three are extremely important changing procedure where the comma or period will be outside or inside closing quotation marks.

d) The environment of style: what is a style guide and how to use it?

A style guide is defined in Wikipedia as follows:

A style guide or manual of style is a set of standards for the writing, formatting and design of documents. It is often called a style sheet, although that term also has other meanings.

The standards can be applied either for general use, or be required usage for an individual publication, a particular organization, or a specific field. (Wikipedia, 2019).

The main objective remains for many writers to have a final presentation that fits with expectations. In case we are in front of customers, needs should be taken in consideration. The debate is diverse in the use of the elements of styles. The main difference with punctuation or literature and grammar can vary and adopted but the style is subject of different point of views and may vary from “the use of abbreviations,” “the use of headings,” “the use of symbols,” “the structure,” “spelling with UK or English” (EUCLID 2019, 25). Another definition can be taken in consideration:

A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent. Style guides are generally associated with certain types of writing like technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting. In each of these cases, there is a need to ensure that the writing style is consistent and so guidelines are usually published to allow more than one author to contribute while ensuring that the finished piece does not necessarily carry the personal style of the writer but that of the publication, company or website associated with the writing (EUCLID 2019, 24).

The main objective with style guide is to ensure proper communication changing and depends on discipline : scientists, writers , lawyers, diplomats .This may vary, even industries, companies, universities can set a referenced style guide to use to enhance their professional works and consistency in what they are producing for a public.

I think that all these style guides are important points for making a great work and push to formally adopt a way of working. Having a style guide in companies I have been working for, was to properly brand in a perspective of showing a graphic design and a language. This create all the time a unique vision, adopted around the world as the Chicago Manual of style, and remain an answer to many companies fascinating with their image.

i) *American and British English*

We were facing something essential in the world, America was influencing everything around the world even with their language. We have many repercussions on the perception and use of English in some areas. Many differences rise with UK English compared to US English. The ECONOMIST defines “a ‘movie’ is used to describe big American-style Hollywood films, whereas ‘film’ is more of a small-scale, maybe independent film. The ‘chips’ that you have in a good old British ‘fish and chips’ shop are very different from the ‘fries’ you get in an American-style fast food restaurant.” (The Economist, 2017). As shown in this example, differences are not only in writing. Differences are multiples in the way of pronunciation, punctuation, syntax. An example, common use in our academic papers will be the honorifics: Mr. or Mrs. or Dr. Smith (U.S.) vs Mr or Mrs or Dr. Smith (GB) (EUCLID 2019, 29).

As far as I am concerned by these influences from these two parts, I think they are culturally, economical, sociologic and each society tends to give a big interest in what they have in their own society. Expressions are diverse and remain the important part of a

community's face. As African, born in a francophone area, these differences were not assimilated at the beginning, but going through these materials, I learnt a lot in what we have to give, presenting to other even an academic work. Presentation is an expression and the way we tackle them, shows one part of ourselves.

ii) *Chicago rules (Turabian)*

This style is originally used by students for citing and referencing during their studies and researches, a focal point to restate their works in a good academic way, using the manual of Turabian Sources citation notes and bibliography as well as author-date. They are used in different context properly.

The first one is defined as: "The notes and bibliography style is popular in the humanities including literature, history, and the arts. In this system, sources are cited in numbered footnotes or endnotes" (The Chicago Manual of Style, 2017).

And in another register:

The author-date style is more common in the physical, natural, and social sciences. In this system, sources are briefly cited in the text, usually in parentheses, by author's last name and year of publication. Each citation in the text matches up with an entry in a reference list, where full bibliographic information is provided (The Chicago Manual of Style, 2017).

The use can be totally different as mentioned previously and adopt certain rules which are related to the academic fields. When giving these definitions we can consider also:

Turabian's A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations continues a tradition of providing one of the best interpretations of The Chicago Manual of Style for higher education students and researchers in this ninth edition. The writing style is clear and easy to read, with examples illustrating proper formatting of items (Cynthia Goode, 2019).

I think these works are technical for a new student but it is important to share works with an instructor at the beginning to avoid any kind of missuses. Reading and researches can complete as well as giving a credit in front of readers. Be more curious and exchange where needed with other students will be helpful.

3) **CONCLUSION**

This first period Aca-401 brought to our attention many rules, on how to write an academic work. Some were not assimilated at the beginning or not known. But now, we gain a lot with such academic materials. Using Zotero was an easy process but most helpful in referencing an academic work.

My proper English level is reinforced by this period, an improvement of my skills in English. I understand from now that many studies as well as works need a logical flow, an esthetical presentation which gives easily a perception of ideas to express. From a simple way, I now understand how important to be meticulous presenting academic works.

Each part was totally helpful from the beginning to the end. I am impregnated with argumentations that should be presented, for sure these materials have to be recommended to all friends and other students for a great academic work. We need to express ourselves in the right manner, to be understandable, what William Butler Yeats defines in these words “Think like a wise man but communicate in the language of the people.”

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